

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE PROMINENT SCIENTIST WHO PLAYED THE INVALUABLE ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORICAL SCIENCE IN AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

Historical science has always distinguished with its outstanding personalities. These people, possessing unique talents, abilities, skills and scientific braveness that have passed through the filter of time, have said, say and will say their words in history. Despite all the difficulties they faced, the unique talent of these scientists, the desire to work and fight tirelessly called them to science and made them to gain new achievements and successes. Science is a great sea. The people who work in this field are quite hardworking, brave and capable of overcoming all the obstacles that come their way, geniuses. From this point of view, the outstanding personality of Azerbaijan historical science, the person of unique talent, creative ability, ability to honestly analyze historical facts as they are, endless desire to work, great diligence, scientific insight and genius, wonderful scientist, genius person, great hard work and irreplaceable educator Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is a prominent figure of science who has known the field in which she is all over the world. As one of the most prominent figures of the modern era, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is the invaluable historian, her creativity, activity, hard work and endless achievements in science should be the object of serious research. This outstanding historian scientist, who has been working steadily in historical science for many years and achieved high results in her field, has always the huge role in the development of historical science and was distinguished by the point that she looks at historical events only through the eyes of real facts.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, historical science, prominent scientist, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, invaluable role, scientific activity, creativity, educator, top of science, genius.

Introduction

Azerbaijan, which has an ancient history, has always heroically emerged from the difficult trials and obstacles of history and wrote the chronicle of bravery in history. Our country, which is proud of its heroic children and patriots, is also known for its outstanding personalities, scientists, persons who have spoken their word all over the world and have extraordinary scientific consciousness and insight, distinguished by their hard work, unique talent, skills and abilities, endless love for education and science, desire to work and fight tirelessly.

Azerbaijan historical science does not stand still like other branches of science, it is constantly developing. Since the 60s of the XX century, special features began to form in the historical science of Azerbaijan and found this embodiment in the creativity of young, talented historians. These individuals, who tried to have their say and follow their own path in the development, formation, maturation and establishment of the science of history as a science, who tried to overcome all the obstacles and difficulties they faced in this field, who were particularly distinguished by their original creative style, talent, skills and abilities and endless hard work, who always relied only on real facts in the topics they addressed and in the fields they worked in, and who always remained faithful to the science of history during their scientific activities, can be considered the most prominent figures in the history of Azerbaijan. The works written during this period and the historical writings that have been established indicated the formation of new outstanding personalities of the future in

the historical science of Azerbaijan. One of such outstanding personalities is the well – known Azerbaijani historian, turkologist, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, the excellent scientist and best educator with exemplary morality and excellent moral values, who has never distorted historical facts, constantly stood on real events and facts in her work, mobilized all her forces, skills and abilities to overcome obstacles and difficulties faced in the field of science.

Since the 60s of the XX century as an intellectual who selflessly contributed to the development of historical science, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva has worked tirelessly on the difficult path and her great scientific activity played the decisive role in her full formation as the scientist and transformation into the wonderful specialist.

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, who has always been distinguished only by her high consciousness and insight, rare talent, great hard work and love for science, can be characterized by her unique activity in the development of various branches of historical science. In this regard, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's scientific research and fundamental works in the field of highlighting the activities of creative unions, studying the new era of the history of the Turkic peoples and etc. are quite noteworthy.

The scientific activity combines constant hard work, great attention, serious concentration on every little thing to be done, analysis of historical events and the scientist's worldview, broad worldview, complete formation of personality in the period before scientific activity, honest historical assessment of existing events

and facts, selection of bad from good, non – distortion of facts, focusing only on real facts in writing history, formation of science as real science, etc., which are very necessary and important elements. A scientist who does not possess these elements and does not constantly work on himself will never be able to develop the field of science in which he operates. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, who has such values, skills and abilities, excellent talent, oratory art, excellent scientific insight and consciousness, great conscience, honesty and Academic Honor, is an intellectual who has made the great contribution to the development of Azerbaijani historical science for many years.

Intelligence has brought up its valuable representatives as a class that always taken the side of the right and tried to protect them from the existing threats, expressing their attitude to the events taking place in the life of society with its fighting theme. The intelligentsia was always at the forefront against the background of historical events, tried to reveal the true image and face of historical processes, illuminated people with the light of the intelligentsia and called for honesty, always developed education and science and tried to protect them from shortcomings. From this point of view, the

activity of prominent historian, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva as the well – known intellectual is characterized by her uniqueness, deep scientific knowledge and based on real facts.

Scientific and labor activity

In 1960 young Nisbet Mehdiyeva graduated from the faculty of history of Azerbaijan State University. In 1960 – 1963 she worked as the researcher at the Institute of history of the Academy of Sciences of the Azerbaijan SSR. Nisbet Mehdiyeva was a full – time graduate student at Azerbaijan State University in 1964-1967. In 1967 – 1973 she worked as a teacher and senior lecturer at the Azerbaijan State Medical Institute. Young Nisbet Mehdiyeva defended her PhD thesis on the topic “The Struggle of the Azerbaijani Trade Unions for the Restoration of the Oil Industry under the Leadership of the Party (1921 – 1925)” in 1968. She was an acting associate professor and associate professor at Azerbaijan State University from 1973 to 1991. In 1991, Nisbet Mehdiyeva defended her doctoral dissertation entitled “Activity of Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of development of Culture (1960 – 1980s)”. In 1991 – 1994 she was an acting professor at Baku State University and since 1994 she has been a professor.

Image 1. Young historian scientist Nisbet Mehdiyeva

Young historian scientist Nisbet Mehdiyeva [Image 1] as the fields of research social organizations, Creative Unions and societies, cultural problems, history of Turkic peoples and etc. she dealt with issues and wrote research works on them. In her PhD thesis defended in 1968, the scientist was involved in the research in detail in almost all leading areas of Azerbaijan, including the great struggle and practical work carried out by the Trade Unions of Azerbaijan in the oil industry. The author has investigated the important and decisive role of Trade Unions in the labor activities of citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan in protecting

workers and labor rights, attracting people to work, organizing conscious and efficient labor and at the same time improving the livelihoods of workers in her research work based on real facts. She carefully approached the problems of labor organization, increasing its efficiency, protecting the rights and freedoms of employees, ensuring occupational safety in the work process, protecting the health of employees as one of the most important issues, etc. The author has seriously studied the effective activities and continuous struggle of the Azerbaijani Trade Unions and written them at a fundamental level [17].

Image 2. Doctor of Historical Sciences Nisbet Mehdiyeva

Already in 1991, the young candidate of historical sciences Nisbet Mehdiyeva, having studied the activities of the Azerbaijani Creative Unions in the field of cultural development in the 1960 – 1980s, presented and defended a new fundamental scientific – research work – a doctoral dissertation on this topic [Image 2]. This is the first doctoral dissertation dedicated to the history of the Creative Unions in the former USSR [16].

The period of activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the 1960 – 1980s is quite rich and shows the scale and necessity of the huge work done in this field. The Creative Unions, engaged in artistic activity, tirelessly carried out propaganda and agitation work in the field of cultural development.

The author conducted a large – scale research work on the moral and spiritual values, aesthetic worldview, knowledge and skills, spiritual world of people, growth and formation as an adult, revealing creative and talented people, playing of culture a decisive role in the development of other fields of science, investigating the intense and necessary work of creative intellectuals in solving the problems of humanity and citizens, the difficulties and obstacles they face daily and involving their fields of activity in research and scientific analysis. The unique individual work carried out by each Creative Union in the field of development of culture has become the object of research of valuable researcher and scientist Nisbet Mehdiyeva and the scientific and artistic activity played by the creative intel-

ligentsia in the field of research of theoretical and practical problems of modern culture has been brought to attention.

The Creative Unions have regularly conducted various practical events to determine the main development directions of the country`s culture, organized the discovery, protection, publication, dissemination, promotion, education, etc. of rare works of classical and modern times, promoted the art and creativity of prominent creative intellectuals, protected valuable personnel and intellectuals, evaluated their valuable works of art and samples, etc. [10].

Nisbet Mehdiyeva, a scientist who defended her doctoral dissertation on the activities of the Azerbaijani Creative Unions in the field of development of Culture in the 1960 – 1980s and received the degree of Doctor of Historical Sciences, is one of the first valuable and talented researchers in Azerbaijan to write such a fundamental work in this field.

Thus, the valuable scientist Nisbet Mehdiyeva has written another fundamental work, conducting an accurate analysis of the important role of the significant part played by the Azerbaijani Creative Unions in the development of Azerbaijani culture, their impact on the spiritual development of society and the achievements and shortcomings in the field of cultural development.

The scientific value and novelty of this study is that for the first time in the work, the activities of the Creative Unions of Azerbaijan in the field of development of Culture were investigated in such a broad aspect and involved in serious research.

Image 3. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva [Image 3] continued to work on the topic, expanding her research in this field and in 2014 wrote a fundamental monograph entitled “The activities of the Azerbaijani Creative Unions in the field of development of Culture (1960 – 1980s)”. The monograph reflects the issues of the activities of the Writers` Union, the Composers` Union, the Artists` Union, the Theater Workers` Union and the Cinematographers` Union in the field of development of culture in Azerbaijani historiography. The ideological – political level and professional mastery of creative intellectuals, the creative and organizational work of unions, their role in the promotion of artistic culture and the problem of their activity in the field of cultural relations are investigated with great precision in the work.

The work is of great interest as a research object. The scope of activities of the unions is quite wide, significant and unique. Along with the explanation and presentation of the achievements and successes achieved in the process of development of each issue, the author did not ignore the shortcomings and mistakes made [11].

While working on these topics, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva was able to provide detailed explanations of the new way of understanding and issues related to the discovery of various facts in the research process.

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is also the author of a wonderful research work – a textbook – on the new era of the history of the Turkic peoples. Her fundamental work entitled “History of the Turkic peoples. New era (XIX – early XX centuries)” covers new era of the Turkic peoples, the socio – political processes faced by the region in this period, the administrative – management system, political situation, various events in the life of the Turkic peoples, the difficulties and problems they face, the economic situation, cultural problems, etc., relevant areas and topics [4] [5].

While the author involved the Turkic peoples in the XIX and early XX centuries in her research, she investigated the region`s integration into a unified administrative system before, during and after the occupation, the gradual decline of the feudal – patriarchal administrative system in the territories inhabited by the Turkic peoples and the formation of capitalist relations, the role and importance of the Turkic peoples in various socio – political processes during this period and the position they took in the course of events. Unlike other scholars working in this field, the author succeeded in studying the events based on real facts and sources. This fundamental work by Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva was published in 2003 and 2010. The textbook is a valuable source in the field of studying and teaching the new era of the history of the Turkic peoples (XIX – early XX centuries) and can be considered a very valuable scientific resource.

At different times, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva has investigated the characteristic features and unique aspects of the new era of the Turkic peoples by involving them in scientific research, including changes in the administrative – management system of the Turkic peoples in the XIX – early XX centuries [2, 37 – 39], the state of the education system in Turkestan and the problems it faces [8, 40 – 42], the development of science in the peoples of the region and the socio – political situation that created conditions for it [13, 37 – 39], issues of statehood of the Turkic peoples [12, 50 – 53], problems of the promotion and development of enlightenment [3, 271 – 273], the scientific societies and organizations operating in this region, their scientific expeditions and fundamental works they wrote [9, 107 – 110], the fruitful work and areas of activity carried out by the periodical press and cultural – educational institutions here [7, 342 – 345], cultural problems [14, 23], global issues [15, 295 – 298] and etc.

Image 4. Educator Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva has also been engaged in pedagogical activity for many years [Image 4]. Thanks to her great efforts, great pedagogical work has been done in the area of perfect mastery, teaching and promotion of education and science by hundreds of students, including the transformation of education into one of the leading areas. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva has taught undergraduate courses in the subject “History of the Turkic Peoples. New and Modern Period” and graduate courses in the problems of “Socio – political situation in Central Asia, Kazakhstan, the Volga region, Siberia and Crimea (XIX – early XX centuries)” and “Culture of the Turkic Peoples (XIX – early XX centuries)”.

In connection with pedagogical activity, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva has written a textbook for higher education institutions “History of the Turkic peoples. New era (XIX – early XX centuries)” [4] [5], 8 textbooks for secondary schools (2001, 2002, 2004, 2005 and 2007) (in the first and revised editions), a teaching aid [1], 1 methodological instruction [6], 11 programs and etc.

The scientific and pedagogical activity of the prominent representative of the historical science of Azerbaijan, bravely and heroically withstood all the obstacles and difficulties of science, developing the historical science in which it operates, constantly moving it forward, Young and evergreen historian scientist, great personality and educator, professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is very valuable.

Conclusions

History is always proud of its heroic sons. Such individuals have always been at the forefront and have been particularly distinguished by their high moral and spiritual values, talent, skills and abilities, unimaginably great hard work, tireless work in the development of education and science, the recognition of the country with the honesty it deserves all over the world, their high personal qualities, etc. They have always been at the forefront and have been particularly distinguished by their superior qualities. Such people have already

been formed as personalities over time and have demonstrated valuable characteristics such as endless enthusiasm, optimism, loyalty to their work and reliability in history and in the spheres they work and operate.

Due to her profound talent, high scholarly sense and genius, consciousness and insight, great talent, skills and abilities, broad outlook, rich scientific and pedagogical experience, endless desire to learn and teach, endless love for life, people and her country, fighting spirit, enthusiasm for living and working, bravely overcoming all the difficulties and obstacles she faced, rich pedagogical and scientific heritage, etc., Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is a great scientist, intellectual and enlightened person, an irreplaceable personality. The huge role played by Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva in the development of Azerbaijani historical science is undeniable.

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